

Agrivoltaics for Backyard Farming - focused on the technical and social aspects exemplified on Mahé, Seychelles

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Introduction to the study

Anthropogenic climate change poses a severe global challenge, with Small Island Developing States (SIDS) like Seychelles being particularly vulnerable. Issues such as rising temperatures, extreme rainfall, droughts, and water scarcity severely impact agriculture and threaten local food production and security. With about 90% of food being imported, global crises like the COVID-19 pandemic and wars further exacerbate food supply risks and drive up prices (GIZ, 2014, p.6; Government of Seychelles, 2019, p.71-73; Etongo, 2023, p.1).

Furthermore, Seychelles predominantly relies on imported heavy oils for electricity generation. More than 95% of the nation's primary energy supply comes from imported fuels (Public Utilities Corporation, n.d., p.11; Government of Seychelles, 2019, p.72). This dependence leads to high vulnerability to fluctuations in oil prices, elevated costs for electricity supply due to limited economies of scale and a complex, resource-intensive transportation system (Government of Seychelles, 2012, p.187; Stock, 2014, p.6-7).

In summary, this emphasizes the strong dependency on imports and underscores the need for a reevaluation of agricultural practices. Additionally, the urgent expansion of renewable energies is imperative, especially given the continuously increasing energy demand (Public Utilities Corporation, n.d., p.10-11; The Seychelles National Climate Change Committee, 2009, p.23). Moreover, it highlights the importance of self-sufficiency for private households in the island nation of Seychelles.

The Government of Seychelles strives to achieve greater independence from other countries by promoting local food production, including supporting backyard farming and strengthening sustainability. In addition, Seychelles is also committed to increasing its renewable energy usage with a target of 100% renewable energy supply (van Vreden et al., 2010, p.9; Government of Seychelles, 2012, p.187 and 2013, p.10; Republic of Seychelles, 2015, p.8; Government of Seychelles 2019, p.74). As about half of the total land area is under protection, agriculture and energy generation on land is challenging (Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2013, p.3).

To achieve these objectives and mitigate land competition among various interests, Agrivoltaics for backyard farming could prove to be a viable component of the solution. For the purpose of this study, backyard farming is defined as agricultural activities conducted on farmland with no minimum size but capped at <1000 m². For larger areas, primarily self-consumption with minimal surplus sales is required. Households cultivating only trees were excluded, based on the assumption that Agrivoltaics is unsuitable for such setups. Farming includes cultivating crops for consumption and livestock husbandry.

Seychelles has recognized the potential of Agrivoltaics and, in March 2024, completed the Technology Assessment (TA) in collaboration with the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). Following a review of national development plans and technologies, the decision was made to promote 'Agrivoltaics for fully controlled environment crop production' (UNCTAD, 2024b, p.1-2). This concept involves indoor and vertical farming combined with hydroponics, aquaponics, or aeroponics (DSTI, 2024, p.8). The evaluation of this technology is ongoing (UNCTAD, 2024a, p.49). In August 2024, a study on Agrivoltaics focusing on acceptance among commercial farmers on Mahé was published in the Seychelles Research Journal (Weber and Rothstein, 2024, p.39-57). This study contributes to advancing research on Agrivoltaics in tropical climates and SIDS like Seychelles.

However, Agrivoltaics remains a nascent technology, and many research questions still require foundational groundwork. Given the lack of existing studies or projects on Agrivoltaics regarding backyard farming, this research addresses an unexplored topic, underscoring its importance.

Given that the main island of Mahé houses approximately 88% of the Seychellois population, it was determined that limiting the research focus to this area would still yield findings representative enough for the entire country (National Bureau Of Statistics, 2022, p.4).

Objective of the investigation

This research aims to assess the potential of Agrivoltaics regarding backyard farming on Mahé, Seychelles. The term 'potential' is broadly defined, encompassing and complex. To analyse this potential, both technical and social aspects are discussed in this paper, with the goal to establish a foundation and prerequisite for further studies.

This objective is divided into three sub-goals. *The first goal* is to develop a quantitative survey intended for backyard farmers on Mahé. This will involve comprehensive literature research and consultation with experts. *The second goal* is to conduct a survey with the backyard farmers to obtain a comprehensive local overview and gauge general sentiment.

In particular, the survey results will be used to analyse the social aspects, specifically examining the perception of Agrivoltaics. *The third goal* is to evaluate the technical aspects based on the survey results. This will include a site assessment for potential energy output and the level of self-sufficiency.

Research methodology

This section outlines the methodological approach and the associated objectives of the survey as well as the social and technical analyses.

Survey with backyard farmers

It was decided to design a quantitative questionnaire as the data collection tool, allowing for descriptive analysis. Additionally, to facilitate understanding of an Agrivoltaics system, illustrative examples were compiled using images for visualization.

To develop the questionnaire, a comprehensive literature review was initially conducted. In addition to the literature review, local experts were also questioned to gain a general overview and to get detailed information. Individuals from the institutions of the Agriculture Department (Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment), Energy Commission, Agriculture Producers Association of Seychelles, The Division of Science, Technology, and Innovation (DSTI), Department of Environment (UniSey), and Ministry of Land Use and Housing were questioned. Furthermore, discussions were held with small-scale farmers at fruit and vegetable stands.

The survey is divided into four different sections. The first part deals with *backyard farming*, the second with *electricity consumption*, followed by the *perception of Agrivoltaics*, and concludes with the *social-demographic background*.

The first part includes eleven items on topics like backyard farming area, land use, shading effects, crops benefiting from shade, irrigation, water source, and self-sufficiency. Questions about crop growth height were omitted to simplify responses, focusing instead on the type of agriculture practiced.

The second part contains five items and provides information about household size, grid connection, electricity consumption, time of greatest consumption, and how important it is for the respondent to be independent from fluctuating electricity prices.

The third part has five questions focusing on perceptions of Agrivoltaics' barriers and opportunities, land suitability, desired support, and interest in community-based Agrivoltaic systems.

The last part addresses the social-demographic background. Information was collected on age, occupation, and monthly household income.

Following the approach of Arundel and Döring, some items were measured using a five-point Likert-Scale (Arundel, 2023, p.39; Döring, 2023, p.270-272). This type of question is very common in the social sciences and is particularly effective for evaluating dimensions of perception (Döring, 2023, p.270-271).

Participants could select 'Yes/No' answers or use an 'Other' option to provide alternative responses. Some questions required open-ended answers, such as numerical data or free text for crop names, occupations, or justifications. Multiple responses were allowed for several items, and qualitative remarks were included under 'Further comments'.

Based on Lynn's suggestion, it was decided to conduct a random sample, also known as implicitly stratified sampling (ISS) (Lynn, 2019, p.253). The standard error might be smaller in this approach, and the accessibility of the unit of analysis determined who was included in the sample.

The survey was pretested in a paper-pencil format through face-to-face interviews with three randomly selected participants. During the period from January to February 2024, a total of 29 participants were surveyed. The analysis of the results took place from March to April 2024.

Analysis of the potential energy output and self-sufficiency level

To more accurately assess the potential of Agrivoltaics based on technical aspects within the surveyed sample, the potential energy output and self-sufficiency level were calculated for each site. PVGIS was chosen for the PV simulation. For the analysis, data on electricity consumption and potential farming areas suitable for Agrivoltaics were extracted from the survey results.

General assumptions and module variation

1 year = 360 days

Electricity consumption per day is always the same

No shading of the modules (according to survey results)

No row spacing of the PV modules

According to Quaschnig $\eta_{PV} = 22\%$ (mean) for the calculation of E_{ideal} (Quaschnig, 2024, p.208-209)

Table 1: PVGIS assumptions for all locations of the surveyed participants

Location	-4.657, 55.454
Solar radiation (PVGIS-SARAH2)	1938.25 kWh/m ² ,a
PV technology	Crystalline silicon
System loss	14%
Mounting position	free-standing
Slope (optimized)	0°
Azimuth	0°
Calculated horizon	
Discharge cutoff limit	30%
Battery capacity	6000 Wh

The listed assumptions (input options) in Table 1 were not changed for any of the locations.

Table 2: Module variation

	Peak power	
Module B48/6 (Grid Parity)	137 Wp/m ²	bifacial, 40% transparency
Min. 'Module' Fraunhofer ISE	25 Wp/m ²	
Max. 'Module' Fraunhofer ISE	80 Wp/m ²	

Table 2 displays the module variation and the corresponding peak power. A typical PV module (B48/6) specifically designed for Agrivoltaics by Grid Parity was selected. The transparency level of 40% played a crucial role in the selection. The survey with backyard farmers and discussions with local experts revealed that there is not much experience with high shading in cultivation on Mahé, and a high degree of transparency is generally preferred. Fraunhofer ISE reports performance values for interspace systems ranging from 25-43 Wp/m² and for overhead systems from 50–80 Wp/m² (Trommsdorff et al., 2024, p.50). To compare minimal and maximal PV output with the module from Grid Parity, a range of at least 25 Wp/m² to a maximum of 80 Wp/m² was chosen.

The analysis was conducted in week sixteen of 2024.

Results

The following sections present the descriptive results of the survey, followed by the technical potential – energy output and self-sufficiency level – of the backyard farmers.

Demographic background

The age distribution of the survey participants is evenly spread across the middle and older age groups. Most participants fall into the 25 to 40-year-old category (34%), followed by those aged 40 to 60 (31%), and those over 60 (28%). Overall, the age structure is diverse, with younger individuals under 25 years making up only 7% of this specific sample (n= 29 participants).

The participants reported various occupations, which were subsequently grouped into categories. The distribution is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Frequencies for occupation category

Occupation category	Frequency	Valid percent
Backyard farming	4	14
General labour & unspecified	1	3
Healthcare & therapy	3	10
Public sector & education	8	28
Retired	5	17
Sales & service industry	3	10
Skilled trades & technical services	4	14
Student	1	3
<i>n</i>	29	

Note: The occupations were categorised afterwards in the analysis.

It is noteworthy that four individuals work as backyard farmers by profession, another four out of eight people from the 'public sector and education' specifically work in the field of agriculture, and five individuals are already retired.

Figure 1 shows that eleven households (41%) have a monthly income between 10,000-25,000 SCR, and six households (26%) have an income of less than 10,000 SCR or no income at all.

Figure 1: Monthly household income of the backyard farmers

Note: The option to select '0 SCR' was implemented during the survey (n= 27 participants)

Figure 2 visualizes the size of the farming areas of the individual participants. Four individuals indicated that their farming area is not directly adjacent to their home. All others have their farming area directly next to their home (n = 29 participants).

Figure 2: Farming area

Note: Combined area for farming purpose, without rocks etc.; only for cultivation and livestock (n = 29 participants)

The median farming area is 400 m². Fourteen out of 29 participants have a farming area below this value. The observed standard deviation is 532 m², indicating a considerable spread of the data around the mean of 522 m².

For the area's division, a mean of 3.7 (median: 4, standard deviation: 1.2) was reported on the Likert-scale. This corresponds to an average farming area between partially disjointed

and mainly connected among the surveyed backyard farmers. The most frequently selected ratings were 3 (partially disjointed, ten out of 29 persons) and 5 (completely connected, ten out of 29 persons).

Table 4 shows the classification of farming areas by land use. Ground-level beds (45.3%) and trees (35.5%) constitute the largest portions of the areas on average. Pots also have a significant share of 10.6%.

Table 4: Agriculture land use

	Trees	Shrubs	Raised bed	Ground-level bed	Pots	Grazing	Shade house	Nursery	Roofing for livestock	Stable	Cage
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
Median	35	0	0	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	35.5	2.1	3.6	45.3	10.6	0.2	0.3	1.7	0	0.4	0.4
Std. Deviation	25.6	7.6	16.1	32.0	19.0	0.9	1.7	4.8	0	1.9	1.2
Minimum	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maximum	80	40	85	95	80	5	9	20	0	10	5
n	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	29	27	27

Note: The colour green shows a suitability for overhead and interspace PV, blue a suitability for only overhead PV and the colour grey shows that this area is not suitable for Agrivoltaics. See detailed description below for Figure 3.

Figure 3 shows the proportion of areas that are generally suitable for Agrivoltaics, categorized by land use. It should be noted that these figures do not account for row spacing of the PV modules. A total of 52.9% of the areas are suitable for overhead and interspace PV, with an additional 5.6% suitable for only overhead PV. This means that, in total, 58.5% of the areas are potentially suitable for Agrivoltaics.

As described in the introduction, it was assumed that trees cultivated on Mahé grow too tall for Agrivoltaics to be feasible (height > 6 m). Therefore, trees were classified as 'not suitable for Agrivoltaics'. Additionally, it was assumed that only 50% of the pots are usable for PV, as the other half are on terraces. Stable and cage areas were excluded, based on the guidelines from the Fraunhofer ISE Institute. The distinction from conventional PV roofs is not entirely clear (Trommsdorff et al., 2023, p.11).

Figure 3: Land use suitability for Agrivoltaics (mean)

Note: DIN 91434 was used as the basis for specifying the clear height (DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., 2021, p.16).

Resulting from the land use distribution, the following suitable farming areas for Agrivoltaics in square meter for the individual participants are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Farming area potentially suitable for Agrivoltaics

It was reported that the land area is on average affected by shading during the day with a mean of 1.8 (median: 2, standard deviation: 0.8) on the Likert-scale. This means the areas are not affected to slightly affected. The most frequently selected rating was 2 (slightly affected, thirteen out of 29 persons), followed by 1 (not affected, 12 out of 29 persons). This indicates a very low level of shading, which is generally positive for the suitability of Agrivoltaics, as it implies higher solar irradiance on the PV modules.

43% of the respondents indicated that they do not have any significant shade sources on their property that affect their farming area during the day. If there was a shade source, trees were most frequently mentioned (46%), see Table 5.

Table 5: Frequencies for shade sources

Shade sources	Frequency	Valid Percent
None	12	43
Trees	13	46
Shrubs	0	0
Buildings	0	0
Others	0	0
Trees & shrubs	1	4
n	28	

Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of crops identified by participants as likely to benefit from shade and which they would consider cultivating. Herbs and spices were most frequently cited, accounting for 31% of responses, followed by chinese cabbage and cabbage at 15%, lettuce at 12.5%, and tomatoes at 9%. Notably, 10% of respondents indicated 'No experience' or 'None,' revealing that a significant proportion have no experience in cultivating crops in shaded conditions.

Figure 5: Crops potentially benefiting from shade

Note: The crops mentioned in the survey as potentially benefiting from shade, which the participants would also cultivate, were categorised afterwards in the analysis. The numbers shown in [] indicate the frequency of the respective category that was given (n = 28 participants)

When specific herbs and spices were mentioned, chili [4], coriander [3], turmeric [2], basil [2], thyme [1], garlic [1], rosemary [1], mint [1], and vanilla [1] were noted.

The 'Others' category encompasses a diverse array of crops mentioned once each, including strawberry, pineapple, sweet pepper, carrots, cassava, beans, celery, spinach, pumpkin and katrepis (*Pimenta racemosa*).

For irrigation, 69% of respondents reported using hand watering. 10% indicated they use both hand watering and micro irrigation, and 7% (two households) do not irrigate their cultivation area at all, see Table 6. Households who do not irrigate stated that their crops do not require additional water.

Table 6: Frequencies for irrigation

Irrigation	Frequency	Valid Percent
No irrigation	2	7
Hand watering	20	69
Sprinkler	0	0
Micro irrigation	2	7
Hand watering & sprinkler	2	7
Hand watering & micro irrigation	3	10
n	29	

As a water source for irrigation, the most frequently mentioned combination was the collection and use of rainwater and PUC water (tap water from the Public Utilities Corporation) (34%). Additionally, 24% reported using natural freshwater, see Table 7.

Table 7: Frequencies for water source

Water source	Frequency	Valid Percent
None	2	7
Natural freshwater	7	24
Rainwater	2	7
PUC water*	3	10
Natural freshwater & rainwater	2	7
Natural freshwater & PUC water*	3	10
Rainwater & PUC water	10	34
n	29	

Note: *PUC water (tap water from the Public Utilities Corporation).

Groundwater and other natural freshwater sources categorised as ‘Other’ during the survey were summarised under ‘Natural freshwater’ in the analysis. Under ‘Other natural fresh water’, springs, wells, rivers or river water from the Val d'Endorre water reservoir (part of the Agriculture Department system) were mentioned. The option to select ‘None’ was implemented during the survey.

Figure 6 clearly shows that it is predominantly very important (scale 4) to extremely important (scale 5) for backyard farmers to be self-sufficient with food. Nine out of 29 people rated this question with a 4, and eighteen out of 29 rated it with a 5 on the Likert-scale.

Figure 6: Importance of food self-sufficiency
(n= 29 participants)

In the additional comments, eleven respondents emphasized the high importance they place on food self-sufficiency, e.g. citing their practice of organic farming and a desire to consume organic food as significant reasons. They believe that organic food is better for their health and perceive imported food as being of low quality. Additionally, they mentioned the high cost of purchasing food and noted that growing their own produce could be a way to save money. Furthermore, they also view the act of growing their own food as a therapeutic activity.

Electricity consumption

The mean household size was 4.2 (median: 3, dtd. Deviation: 2.75), with a minimum of one member and a maximum of fourteen members (n= 29 participants).

All 29 surveyed households have a grid connection. Three of them indicated that they do not have a grid connection on their farming area, and that the farming area is not directly adjacent to their home. Only one household has a grid connection directly on their farming area, which is not adjacent to their home.

The median electricity consumption per household is 315 kWh/month, for which they pay 590 SCR/month. Considering the household size, the consumption per person is 90 kWh/month and 170 SCR/month, see Table 8. Based on these results and those under Figure 4, an analysis of the potential energy output and self-sufficiency level will be conducted.

Table 8: Electricity consumption

	per household [SCR/month]	per person [SCR/month]	per household [kWh/month]	per person [kWh/month]
Median	590	170	315	90
Mean	801	207	360	102
Std. Deviation	822	123	228	49
Minimum	251	39	147	23
Maximum	4420	631	1325	189
n	29	29	29	29

Data refers to prices before 15 January 2024.

The survey identified electricity consumers and their peak times of usage throughout the day. Most electricity consumption occurs in the morning and evening. Common appliances with the highest consumption include washing machines, dishwashers, ovens, refrigerators and air conditioners.

Regarding cooking methods, seventeen households reported cooking exclusively with gas, five use only an electric oven (with a gas stove), and five rely entirely on electricity for cooking. Additional details are available in Appendix 4 (n= 27 participants).

Figure 7 shows how important it is for respondents to be independent from external electricity sources, such as the PUC or other countries. It can be seen that a strong majority (eight out of 29 people) find it very important and even extremely important (fifteen out of 29 people). It is noteworthy that during the survey, it was found that no household produces its own electricity for personal use, such as with a rooftop photovoltaic system. However, two households have small PV modules to power lights on their terraces (personal notes).

Figure 7: Importance of external electricity independence

Moreover, in the additional comments, two respondents mentioned that it would be important for them to be independent from external electricity, due to occasional power outages from PUC. Another person noted that increasing this independence would also enhance electricity security.

Perception of Agrivoltaics

Figure 8 shows that, on average, six out of twelve barriers received a rating above 3 on the Likert-scale. The main barrier identified was 'Investment costs' (rating = 4.4), followed by 'Others' (rating = 4.4) and 'Funding options' (rating = 4.0). Under 'Others', 'Stealing' was mentioned six times (rating = 4.2), 'Damage caused by storm and/or thunder' once (rating = 5), and 'Fluctuating electricity production' once (rating = 4). Only two households are not the owners of their property (one is on government land and one is rented).

Figure 8: Barriers

Note: *Potential damage to PV modules caused by surroundings. **Bird and fruit bats could perch on the installation. For ownership of cultivation area were rated 1 = none (private property) or 5 = very strong (governmental land or rented) (n= 29 participants, for others: n= 7 participants)

Figure 9 shows that all opportunities received an average rating above 3 on the Likert-scale. The main opportunity identified was 'Others,' followed by 'More electricity security' and 'Crop protection.' Under 'Others,' 'Prevent stealing with cameras, sensors, or lights' was mentioned twice (rating = 5), 'Extra income with electricity production' once (rating = 5), 'New electricity possibilities, e.g., light control for security or PV-water pump' once (rating = 3), and 'Showcasing for neighbours' once (rating = 5).

In the additional comments, one respondent also mentioned that 'More diverse cultivation possibilities' could include the integration of hydroponics, featuring a water pump,

reservoir, and filter. The person noted that hydroponics is not expensive and requires only the necessary know-how.

Figure 9: Opportunities

(n= 29 participants, for multiple land use n= 28 participants; for others: n= 5 participants)

Overall, all potential opportunities were rated very highly (total mean = 4.0). In contrast, the barriers were rated relatively low (total mean = 2.7).

Figure 10 shows how suitable the respondents perceive their land to be for Agrivoltaics. No one rated their property as unsuitable. Ten out of 29 people rated their property as very suitable (rating = 4), and seven out of 29 people rated it as extremely suitable (rating = 5).

Additionally, under the further comments seven individuals explicitly expressed interest in Agrivoltaics: they want to know the next steps and recommendations; in general, they wish for more education on renewable energies; they would like to implement Agrivoltaics and general PV usage, (including battery storage); the combination of shade houses with PV could be interesting; one noted that having flat land makes them consider Agrivoltaics and they questioned the difficulty of implementation.

Furthermore, it is noteworthy that one household is already planning to install Agrivoltaics in combination with hydroponics. They aim to implement water treatment using a water pump in their backyard and would like to try growing leafy vegetables like cabbage, chinese cabbage, lettuce, tomatoes, capsicum, sweet chili, spices, and spring onions. It should also be mentioned that the surveyed person had previously heard of Agrivoltaics and possesses considerable knowledge in agriculture, as they work professionally in the field.

Figure 10: Suitability of Agrivoltaics
(n= 29 participants)

All support offers are rated above 4 (total mean = 4.5). Under 'Others,' the following were mentioned: 'Help from the Agriculture Department' [3] (rating = 4.3), 'Education' [3] (rating = 5), and 'Good variety of distributors to compare efficiency and price' [1] (rating = 5), see Figure 11. The numbers in [] indicate the frequency of the respective support offer mentioned. Additionally, the following was noted under further comments: 'Gap of technical knowledge; need to be tested and show us the benefits, otherwise people will not invest'; 'Test setup for showcasing is majorly important; we can't see the advantages now.'

Figure 11: Support offers
(n= 29 participants, for others: n= 6 participants)

Figure 12 shows the interest in community based Agrivoltaics. 45% of the respondents are interested, another 45% are not interested, and 10% are undecided.

As reasons, participants under 'Yes' indicated 'Diversifying crop yields in the neighborhood' [8] and 'Less work as an individual through mutual support' [5]. Under 'Other', participants mentioned 'Community building' [1], 'Share knowledge' [1], 'More income' [1], and 'Share technology ideas' [1] (n = 13 participants). Under 'Maybe', the reasons given were 'Some people are difficult' [1] and 'Depending on neighbour' [1] (n= 2 participants). Under 'No', 'Want my own farmland' [4], 'I'm too old' [1] and 'Cooperation not good' [1] (n= 6 participants).

Figure 12: Interest for community-based Agrivoltaics

Note: The option to select 'Maybe' was implemented during the survey. The numbers shown in [] indicate the frequency of the respective category that was given (n= 29 participants)

Participants who indicated 'Yes' or 'Maybe' could envision the following as possible locations: 36% a larger project, e.g., within the district, 57% on a smaller scale with immediate neighbours, and 7% on a smaller scale with family (because neighbours just have guesthouses) (n= 15 participants).

Analysis of the potential energy output and self-sufficiency level

The technical potential for Agrivoltaics in the studied sample is further illustrated below based on the results for potential energy output and self-sufficiency level. Table 9 shows the PV energy output [kWh/a,m²] of the four selected modules. The 'Land use' indicates the respective coverage. For example, the B48/6 module (Grid Parity) was also considered with 50% coverage of the potential suitable farming area (Module No. 2). For Modules 2 and 3, '100% coverage' was chosen, as these are the peak power per area values based on Fraunhofer ISE experience. Module 1 would achieve the highest energy output (204.37 kWh/a,m²), while Module 3 would have the lowest (37.29 kWh/a,m²).

Table 9: PV energy output per m²

No.	Land use	Module	PV energy output
Module 1	100% land use	Module B48/6 (Grid Parity)	204.37 kWh/a,m ²
Module 2	50% land use	Module B48/6 (Grid Parity)	102.19 kWh/a,m ²
Module 3	'100% land use'	Min. 'Module' Fraunhofer ISE	37.29 kWh/a,m ²
Module 4	'100% land use'	Max. 'Module' Fraunhofer ISE	119.34 kWh/a,m ²

In comparison, the ideal PV energy output is 426 kWh/a,m². This ideal value does not consider the performance ratio (PR).

The corresponding mean and median installed peak PV power of the sample are shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Installed peak PV power

Module No.	1	2	3	4
	[kWp]	[kWp]	[kWp]	[kWp]
Median	21	10	4	12
Mean	40	20	7	24
Std. Deviation	49	25	9	29
Min.	0	0	0	0
Max.	230	115	42	135

Table 11 shows the total energy output that could potentially be produced by the Agrivoltaics system, without considering consumption behaviour or the exact configuration of the system. In this case, the produced energy would only be fed into the grid.

Table 11: Total PV energy output (only grid-connected system)

Module No.	1	2	3	4
	[kWh/a]	[kWh/a]	[kWh/a]	[kWh/a]
Median	30656	15328	5594	17901
Mean	60327	30164	11008	35228
Std. Deviation	73390	36695	13391	42856
Min.	715	358	131	418
Max.	343771	171885	62726	200742

Comparing the yield from the PV system with the household consumption reveals the respective factor for each module, as shown in Table 12. Notably, even with Module 3, which has the lowest power peak, a median factor of 1.23 could be achieved. This means that, in principle, more electricity could be produced than is consumed by the households.

Table 12: Factor consumption - PV energy output (only grid-connected system)

Module No.	1	2	3	4
Median	6.74	3.37	1.23	3.77
Mean	16.63	8.32	3.03	8.07
Std. Deviation	20.28	10.14	3.70	8.01
Min.	0.08	0.04	0.01	0.04
Max.	95.49	47.75	17.42	22.15

Assuming the households have a PV self-consumption system with a battery storage capacity of 6000 Wh, even Module 3 results in a median PV energy output of 3780 kWh/a, see Table 13. In this analysis, the consumption behaviour (daily fluctuations in electricity usage), including what is consumed directly and what is first stored in the battery, is considered. The PV energy output is therefore lower than that in Table 11, as the 'Unutilized energy' – that is, the energy fed into the grid – is not included (median difference of 1814 kWh/a). The self-sufficiency level would be an impressive 66% in the median.

Table 13: Total PV energy output (PV self-consumption-system with battery, grid-connected)

	Needed grid-supply [Wh/day]	PV energy output [kWh/a]	Self-sufficiency Level [%]
Median	3778	3780	66
Mean	5950	2176	57
Std. Deviation	6726	1142	27
Min.	445	115	1
Max.	28763	5545	94

Note: The results have been calculated for module 3. This module represents the lowest performance in comparison and thus can illustrate the minimum self-sufficiency level

Interpretation of results

The obtained results will now be contextualised and interpreted in the following sections, considering technical and social aspects, and incorporating current research findings, projects, and local conditions.

Technical aspects

The finding that 25 out of 29 surveyed households have their farming area directly adjacent to their home suggests that this is also true for the majority of backyard farmers on Mahé. This situation allows the electricity produced by the PV system to be used directly for

household demand. Even if the home is not directly adjacent, an Agrivoltaic system can still be beneficial for personal use, for example, to power a water pump on-site.

On average, the agricultural areas are partly disjointed to mainly connected (Likert-scale: 3.7). This is a positive value and can favour the implementation of Agrivoltaics. Additionally, the farming areas are, on average, not or only slightly shaded during the day (Likert-scale: 1.8). The initial rough analysis that 58.5% of the agricultural areas of backyard farmers are generally suitable for Agrivoltaics also shows that there is high regional potential. Furthermore, as of 2010, considering that potentially more than 16,500 households (out of approximately 25,000) engage in farming in Seychelles, there is significant potential here (Seychelles Agricultural Agency and National Bureau Of Statistics, 2013, p.5).

An average self-sufficiency level of 66% indicates that Agrivoltaics could greatly enhance electricity self-sufficiency. Factors like PV capacity, battery size, and annual electricity use affect this level, which could improve with additional rooftop PV modules. While assumptions in the calculation may cause variations, the analysis indicates significant potential benefits for Mahé households.

However, it can be said that, based on the existing results showing a tendency for peak power consumption in the mornings and evenings, a battery system can be beneficial. Otherwise, early in the morning and late in the evening, when solar irradiance is not high, there may not be enough self-produced electricity available. Assuming no grid integration of the PV system and no battery, the produced electricity would otherwise remain unused. Financially, it makes sense to use the electricity yourself if it can be consumed and to accumulate a buffer with the battery. Only when the storage is full should it be fed into the grid. A private household on Mahé receives 1.67 SCR/kWh (0.88×1.90 SCR/kWh) for feeding into the grid (Public Utilities Corporation, 2021, n.p.). In comparison, the average domestic electricity tariff for grid consumption is 2.30 SCR/kWh (without demand charge, as of 2023) (Public Utilities Corporation 2024, n.p.).

For the technical design, both interspace and overhead mounting structures could be considered. However, this depends on the willingness to invest, the growth height, the desired shading, and the protection function of the farming area. From a technical perspective, bifacial PV modules would be most suitable as they have a higher electrical yield compared to mono-facial modules. This was also confirmed in field trials, such as the feasibility study by Fraunhofer ISE in Maharashtra, India, where an increase of 6.4% was measured (Trommsdorff et al., 2021, p. 1).

Furthermore, it must be considered to what extent Agrivoltaics improves or worsens agricultural circumstances. Agrivoltaics can protect crops from heavy rain, direct radiation, and evaporation through the PV modules. Combining Agrivoltaics with a shade house or nursery is also conceivable. Rainwater collection seems to be quite common

among backyard farmers. 48% of backyard farmers irrigate with rainwater (only rainwater; in combination with rainwater and natural freshwater; or rainwater and tap water from PUC). This is especially important during drought periods. When designing an Agrivoltaic system, special attention should be paid to the drip edge of the PV modules, particularly during heavy rain events. These could be equipped with gutters to mitigate the impact on the soil and to collect additional rainwater. If there is an excess of rainwater, it could also be used for toilets, for example (FAO and ICRISAT, 2019, p.10). Suitable designs for rainwater harvesting can follow studies like the one in Maharashtra, India by Fraunhofer ISE, or the project on the island of La Réunion (Scognamiglio et al., 2014, p.2-3; Trommsdorff et al., 2021, p.1). These adaptations can be seen as a combination of Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA). The use of an Agrivoltaic system can also be considered mitigation, as it utilizes renewable energy.

Participants identified shade-tolerant crops suitable for Agrivoltaics, including herbs, spices, cabbage, lettuce, and tomatoes. Studies for tropical regions confirm some, like turmeric and chili peppers, thrive in shade, with tomatoes showing up to 16% yield increases under reduced evaporation. However, challenges with the greenhouse tomatoes on La Réunion project highlight variability. Passion fruit, successful on La Réunion, though not mentioned in the Mahé surveys, could be explored in future experiments.

Social aspects

Self-sufficiency is very important to extremely important for the backyard farmers on Mahé (27 out of 29 persons). This was also evident from their additional reasons: the importance of organic food, better quality, and the ability to save money. These findings can be partially confirmed by the results of the technical assessment (TA) on Agrivoltaics in Seychelles and another study (Glimmann, 2017, p.63; DSTI, 2024, p.19).

Five out of 27 participants indicated that they cook exclusively with electricity, and five others use an electric oven and a gas stove. All others cook exclusively with gas. In contrast, the Population and Housing Census 2022 showed that 96% use gas as the main source for cooking (National Bureau Of Statistics, 2022, p.50). This indicates that a shift towards sustainability is necessary. Twenty-three out of 29 people stated that independence from external electricity is very important to extremely important to them. Often, the question required an explanation, which could indicate a lack of awareness. Additionally, it was found that none of them have their own power supply source. Furthermore, the electricity tariff is subsidized, which does not reflect the actual costs and does not encourage consumers to save electricity (Government of Seychelles 2012, p.186). This is despite the planned increase in domestic electricity tariffs from 2012 to 2022 (Japan International Cooperation Agency, 2016, p.13-14). Using their own PV system could raise awareness of personal electricity consumption, for example, by general savings or by aligning peak consumption more closely with PV production.

All opportunities for Agrivoltaics were rated highly on average by the backyard farmers surveyed (Likert-scale: 4). Twenty-seven out of 29 households indicated that they own their property, which could positively impact the approval process for the installation. The personal assessment of the backyard farmers regarding the suitability of their land for Agrivoltaics aligns well with the technical evaluation. Seventeen out of 29 individuals rated their property as very suitable to extremely suitable. One household is even planning to install Agrivoltaics in combination with hydroponics, which aligns with the government's plans as outlined in the technical assessment (TA). A community-based project for Agrivoltaics also seems to be a good option, as 45% can envision participating in such a project and 10% are considering it. Based on the survey results, it is recommended to start with small-scale trials.

In contrast, the barriers were rated lower on average, with a score of 2.7 on the Likert-scale. This indicates a general openness to the technology, but also highlights that financing is a significant hurdle (investment costs 4.4 and funding 4.0 on the Likert-scale). This is also reflected in the average rating for the desired financial support offer (Likert-scale: 4.4). This financial barrier, along with the desire for financial support, was also clearly highlighted in the study by Weber and Rothstein on commercial farmers (Weber and Rothstein, 2024, p.55). Overall, all support offers were rated very high on average (Likert-scale: 4.5). This includes the lack of education in renewable energy, specifically Agrivoltaics, and the desire for a test setup as a pilot project. Such a project could demonstrate the benefits of the system and generally test its application on Mahé. The government's TA has already decided to seek funding for such a project. Additionally, they plan to adjust policies to support Agrivoltaics (DSTI, 2024, p.3). Regarding the financing of Agrivoltaics for backyard farmers, rebate schemes should also be introduced, similar to the 'Seychelles Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Programme' (SEEREP) from 2014-2020 or the current rebate scheme for rooftop PV (Hadush and Bhagwat, 2019, p.14-17).

Conclusion and outlook

This research has shown that there is high potential for the implementation of Agrivoltaics in the context of backyard farming on Mahé, both from a technical and social perspective. Notably, the potential average electrical self-sufficiency level of 66% and the openness of backyard farmers towards the technology stand out. Additionally, there is interest from the Agriculture Department, which supported this work, and a general willingness from the government to promote backyard farming to enhance food security (Government of Seychelles, 2013, p.14). Given the limited usable land area on Mahé and the high dependence on external sources for both food and energy supply, it is crucial to consider backyard farming alongside commercial farming. This approach, with suitable

technologies, can contribute to resilience against climate change and ensure energy and food security.

To promote Agrivoltaics for backyard farmers, increase its visibility and awareness among the general population, and test its feasibility, it would be advisable to establish an initial trial site at a research centre, such as the Agriculture Department's Research Station in Anse Boileau or the Institution of Agriculture and Horticulture in Grande Anse. Additionally, education in Agrivoltaics needs to be enhanced not only for backyard farmers, but also for trained personnel in institutions, and technicians on Mahé. Financial support for backyard farmers, such as a rebate scheme, will be necessary, and the feed-in tariff could be raised to the same level as the electricity tariff to be paid in order to provide an incentive. Voluntary compensation measures through tourist donations, promoted by hotels, could also be considered.

Furthermore, it is important to assess the environmental compatibility and impact concerning direct use (soil compaction, water balance, erosion, temperature). Consideration must also be given to the disposal of batteries at the end of their lifespan. It is advisable to conduct economic analyses (investment costs, operating costs, payback time), risk analyses, and utility analyses.

However, further studies are needed to gain a deeper understanding of Agrivoltaics in the context of backyard farming and also for Seychelles, which could help facilitate the transfer of this technology to other tropical regions and Small Island Developing States.

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